

Original article

Can traditional artist's pigments hinder paint binder characterization using immunofluorescence microscopy? Application of widefield fluorescent and confocal laser scanning microscopies for advanced imaging and surface topography scans

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to address the problematics of proteinous binder characterization, within a cross section of painted model samples, using immunofluorescence microscopy. Problems arise from certain pigments which can alter the epitope sites of target binders (lead white and verdigris) or can exhibit a strong natural autofluorescence (lake pigments). Therefore, dual layered model samples were prepared containing a lower egg tempera paint and an upper oil paint, and both paints were made of the same pigment. As an extra challenge for fluorescence microscopy, half of samples were additionally covered with pure linseed oil (as a third layer), which is known to physically reflect fluorescence. Cross-sections were hybridized with anti-ovalbumin antibodies and with FITC labelled secondary antibodies. To reduce unspecific fluorescence, apart from widefield fluorescence, laser-scanning confocal immunofluorescence microscopy was performed. Finally, 3D surface topography models were constructed which were used to check off any unspecific fluorescence originating from cracks or holes. Results show that immunofluorescence microscopy in the widefield observation mode was successful in its specificity and clarity of highlighting the egg paint layer in the presence of 8 out of 10 pigments, including the problematic lead white and verdigris pigments. Several of these pigments (lead white, malachite, yellow ochre, madder lake and carbon black) exhibited autofluorescence; however it was not bright enough to interfere with the successful immunofluorescence microscopy result. In the widefield mode, immunofluorescence microscopy was unsuccessful in the presence of 2 pigments; carmine lake (pigment adsorbs antibodies) and Dragon's blood (pigment dissolved during resin curing at 50 °C). The confocal observation mode in comparison to the widefield mode achieved a much more specific and clear immunofluorescence microscopy picture (especially in the presence of Prussian blue, Vermilion and carbon black) and removed nearly all of the unspecific fluorescence originating from resin's surface reflection, from pure oil binder, from small indentations and from illumination glair that would have otherwise spread across different layers. Lastly, 3D topography models showed that in general samples with smooth surfaces gave a much clearer immunofluorescence microscopy picture.

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1. Introduction

Paintings and polychromies represent one of the earliest modes of expression and are an important part of our shared cultural her-

itage. The pigments used in paint layers are usually mineral powders, but sometimes they are also plant or insect based. Organic binders are added as a fixative for the pigments to form adherent, firm and elastic films with high smoothness, durability and stabilized colour [1–3]. The main distinctive proteins within these binders are gelatine and collagen (animal and bone glues), ovalbumin (egg white) and casein (milk), and the latter two were most

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commonly used in ancient paintings before the advent of oil painting [4]. Even in the later ages, Kockaert et al. [5] and Coremans [6] have noted that in general, blues (glaze-like layers of ultramarine) were more often painted with egg white, where all other colours were oil based. From experience artists knew that due to the yellowing of drying oils, oil based blues (ultramarine) would lose their bright and pure colour.

In multidisciplinary conservation/heritage science, binder characterisation enables for the understanding of past painting techniques and material mixing practises (also for past conservation attempts), the assessment of the degradation rate of organic materials and enables the support for future conservation work (use of appropriate polar/non-polar cleaning solvents etc.) [7]. Moreover, distinguishing their biological origin provides historical information on the derivation and the use of a particular proteinous material [8] and serves as reference for authentication purposes [9].

Currently, only immunofluorescence microscopy is capable of unambiguous proteinous binder identification (together with its biological source) in cross section layers using surface hybridisation of target specific primary antibodies and fluorescent-tagged secondary antibodies [10]. The immuno-complex formation takes place at the polished cross-section of a resin embedded micro sample, which contains exposed epitopes of target proteins [11]. Nevertheless, unspecific fluorescence is still the most important drawback of using widefield (most common) immunofluorescence microscopy in conservation/heritage science [12]. Its intense interfering background emission originates from the unspecific adsorption of antibodies to porous materials, cracks or holes [7,13]. Additionally, dried binders such as oils, natural resins and gelatine glues show a reflecting bright yellow fluorescence [5]. Finally, cracks/gutters between the sample and the embedding polyester acrylic resin also produce reflection.

The application of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) for protein binder identification within painted model samples revealed that certain pigments (especially those containing metal ions) prevented positive reactions, possibly by altering the epitop sites of target proteins [14,15] or by altering the functionality of alkaline phosphatase reporter enzyme [16]. Moreover, Clementi et al. [17] has observed a strong natural autofluorescence of red/yellow lake pigments (carmine lake, etc.) and Kockaert et al. [5] reported colour similarities between the fluorochrome applied in immunofluorescence microscopy and the pigments lead white and zinc white of ancient paintings. Moreover, they recommended that immunofluorescence microscopy should solely be applied on pigments exhibiting no autofluorescence, such as dark pigments (carbon blacks, blues, brown and red earths). Therefore, even though pigments can interfere with immunological detection on various levels, a systematic examination of their impact on immunofluorescence microscopy and on proteinous binder localisation has yet to be conducted.

Therefore, to achieve this within our study, glass supported model samples were created containing a lower egg tempera paint film and an upper oil paint film, and both films were made of the same pigment. Half of samples contained an additional upper layer (third layer) consisting exclusively of dried linseed oil. Cross-sections were hybridized with anti-ovalbumin polyclonal antibodies and with FITC labelled secondary antibodies. Unspecific fluorescence interference was checked by acquiring images before and after antibody hybridization under the same widefield fluorescence illumination conditions. To reduce unspecific fluorescence from dried oil binder and from resin's surface reflection, apart from widefield immunofluorescence microscopy, laser-scanning confocal microscopy was performed. Finally, from 405 nm laser cross-section scans, 3D surface topography models were constructed which were used to check off unspecific fluorescence originating from cracks or holes.

2. Research aim

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of 10 traditional artists' pigments on the efficiency of immunofluorescence microscopy to locate and identify egg tempera paint within a cross-section of a dual/triple-layered model sample. Primarily bright pigments (6 of 10), which exhibit strong autofluorescence, and pigments, which alter the epitope sites of target binders (lead white and verdigris) were selected according to their problematic history recorded in the immunological studies. Moreover, the effect of dried linseed oil, which reflects bright yellow autofluorescence, was examined, by applying it on top of the painted model samples. Lastly, using 3D surface topography scans, the effect of cracks or holes on unspecific fluorescence was carefully evaluated.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Preparation of model samples

A series of 10 model samples was prepared on inert objective glass slide supports (Art No. 42401010; Glasswarenfabrik Karl Hecht GmbH & Co KG), each glass coated with a lower egg tempera paint film and an upper oil paint film, and both films were made of this same pigment. Among the historically most popular pigments, 10 were selected, according to their problematic history recorded in various binder identification studies using immunological detection (see Table 1 for the list of applied pigments, their specifications and relevance).

For the preparation of egg tempera paints, whole egg (egg white and yolk) was employed as a paint vehicle, without additions of water and preservatives. Two free-range chicken eggs were separated from the shell and were thoroughly mixed using a household mixer. After the setting of the liquid, the obtained binder was further mixed with one of the selected pigments using a metal spatula. The forming paint was grinded with a glass muller on a glass plate to an adequate paint consistency (all tools were cleaned with tap water and detergent, and washed with distilled water). For the preparation of oil paint, linseed oil (sun thickened, Kremer Pigmente GmbH & Co.KG; Art.No. 73011.21100.160; CAS: 8001-26-1) was employed as a paint vehicle; and was mixed and grinded with one of the selected pigments using the same procedures as for the egg paint preparation (tempera). The binder to pigment weight ratios of all prepared paints (egg tempera and oil) are noted in Table 1.

Prior to paint application glass supports were cleaned with distilled water and 96% (v/v) ethanol (ACS Reagent). Firstly, egg tempera paints were applied on the frontal planes of glass supports in a single layer with a brush (Utrecht Manglon 2630-B No. 10). All of the prepared samples were left to dry at room temperature, on covered plastic stands, for a period of 2 weeks. After drying, the oil paint was then applied with a brush, in one layer, directly onto the dried layer of the egg tempera paint, which consisted of a matching pigment. After application, the samples were dried for 3 months in sealed paper boxes, so that the top oil layer polymerized nicely and dried thoroughly. For half of the dried samples (containing vermilion, malachite, yellow ochre, madder lake and carbon black), an additional third upper layer, consisting exclusively of fresh linseed oil, was applied with a brush, directly onto the dried layer of the oil paint (second layer). The samples were again dried for 3 months, as described above. After drying, the ageing of all of the prepared samples (dual and triple layered (with the extra fresh linseed oil layer)) was accelerated using the Blak-Ray® XX-15BLB UV Bench Lamps (USHIO, 15 W, 365 nm; 0.6 Amps; 95-0042-11; UVP LLS, USA) for 72 h, at 50% relative humidity and 25 °C.

Table 1

Traditional artists' pigments selected for multi-layered model sample preparation according to their colour, chemical composition, autofluorescence and their possible interference with immunological detection.

Pigment name	Product name*	Product no./ Colour Index*	Chemical formula/Origin	Colour	Relevance	Weight ratio of paint (binder : pigment)	
						Linseed oil	whole egg
Dual layer micro samples						Linseed oil	whole egg
Lead white	Cremnitz White	46,000/PW1, C.I. 77,597	Lead carbonate: Pb(CO ₃) ₂ ·Pb(OH) ₂	White	Reduced ELISA detection [15,18]; and autofluorescence of pigment under immunofluorescence microscopy [5]	1 : 0.76	1 : 0.85
Prussian blue	Prussian blue LUX	45,202/PB27, C.I. 77,510	Iron (III) hexacyanoferrate (II): NH ₄ Fe[Fe(CN) ₆] x 3H ₂ O	Blue	Unknown effects	1 : 0.68	1 : 0.92
Verdigris	Verdigris, synthetic	44,450/PG 20.77408	Copper-(II)-acetate-1-hydrate: (Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·[Cu(OH) ₂] ₃ · 2H ₂ O	Bluish green	Epitope alteration [14]; and reduced ELISA detection [15]	1 : 0.85	1 : 0.83
Carmine lake	Carmine Naccarat	42,100/NR4, C.I. 75,470	Aluminium lake of carminic acid of cochineal origin (Coccus cacti)	Red	Reduced ELISA detection [14]; and red autofluorescence [12,17]	1 : 0.73	1 : 0.86
Dragon's blood	Dragon's Blood, powder	37,000/NR 31.75200, 75,210	Resinous exudation from <i>Daemonorops draco</i> : C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄	Dark red	Autofluorescence of pigment under immunofluorescence microscopy [5]; uninterrupted ELISA detection [15]	1 : 0.79	1 : 0.8
Triple layer micro samples						Linseed oil	whole egg
Vermilion	Vermilion	42,000/PR 106.77766	Mercuric sulfide: HgS	Yellowish red	Autofluorescence of pigment under immunofluorescence microscopy [5]; uninterrupted ELISA detection [14];	1 : 0.73	1 : 0.90
Malachite	Malachite natural, extra fine	10,310/PB 30.77420	Copper hydroxide carbonate: Cu ₂ CO ₃ (OH) ₂	Bright green	Autofluorescence of pigment under immunofluorescence microscopy [5]; uninterrupted ELISA detection [15]	1 : 0.69	1 : 0.98
Yellow ochre	Burgundy Yellow Ochre	11,573/PY 43.77492	Various hydrous iron oxides (limonite), especially goethite (Fe ₂ O ₃ ·H ₂ O)	Yellowish brown	French ochre: uninterrupted ELISA detection [19]	1 : 0.81	1 : 0.79
Madder lake	Madder Lake, genuine	37,202/NR 9.75330, 75,420	Root of the madder plant (<i>Rubia tinctorum</i>): 1,2-dihydroxyanthraquinone	Red	Autofluorescence of pigment under immunofluorescence microscopy [5]	1 : 0.82	1 : 0.84
Carbon black	Cherry Black	12,020/PBk 8.77268	Charred cherry pits (amorphous carbon)	Brownish-black	Unknown effects	1 : 0.80	1 : 0.79

* (Kremer Pigmente GmbH & Co.KG).

3.2. Preparation of cross-sections of micro samples in resin

Firstly, a $\sim 1.5 \times 1.0$ mm large micro sample was removed from the surface of a model sample, using a scalpel. The micro sample was then embed in polyester acrylic resin Kristal PS (Samson Kamnik LLC, Slovenia), containing a 2% concentration (w/w) of catalysator Kristal PS (Methyl ethyl peroxide (MEK); Samson Kamnik LLC, Slovenia). The resin was polymerised for one night at room temperature and further solidified for 1 h in an oven at 50 °C. Hardened micro samples were then polished on the table top polishing equipment RotoPol-15 (Struers Westlake, OH), with six successively finer grades of Micro-mesh abrasive MD-Dac pads (320, 600, 800, 1200, 2400 and 4000 mesh, Struers Westlake, OH), using paraffin oil (Agrolit LLC, Slovenia) as a lubricant. Finally, paraffin oil was removed by sonification (5 min; no heating) of micro samples suspended in petroleum ether (Sigma Aldrich, Germany), using the water bath sonicator Sonis 2 (Iskra PIO LLC, Slovenia). Samples were then carefully wiped, using baby soft tissues (to.to, Tosama LLC, Slovenia), and were fixed onto a microscope glass slide, using a Fimo polymer clay (Staedtler Mars GmbH & Co. KG, Germany), so that the cross sections were facing upwards and were completely aligned with the ground surface.

3.3. Hybridization of antibodies to micro sample cross-sections

First, the exposed cross section was covered with a 50 μ l drop of 5% CSA (N4637, Sigma-Aldrich), which is used as a blocking solution. After a 60 min long incubation period at 23 °C, the blocking solution was removed using a pipette, and 50 μ l of the primary anti-chicken egg albumin antibody (produced in rabbit, Sigma-Aldrich, C6534), diluted in blocking solution (1:10), was pipetted onto each cross section and the micro samples were incubated overnight at 4 °C. Any unbound primary antibody was then washed off, by applying successive 100 μ l drops of PBS at 4 °C to the sample, waiting 5 min, and removing the drop with a pipette. This washing process was repeated three times and great care was taken not to touch the sample itself with the tip of the pipette. After washing, 50 μ l of the FITC (fluorescein isothiocyanate)-conjugated secondary anti-rabbit IgG (produced in goat, Sigma-Aldrich, F0382), diluted in blocking solution (1:10), was pipetted onto each cross section and the micro samples were incubated for 2 h in the dark at 23 °C. Unbound secondary antibodies were washed off, as described above, and during these and all of the subsequent steps, we removed all environmental sources of visible bright light. Finally, any remaining liquid around the micro sample was carefully removed, using a cotton swab (without touching the micro sample itself) and the micro samples were left to dry for 1 h in the dark.

3.4. Microscopy

3.4.1. Reflected-light brightfield observation

Prior to hybridization the sample, cross sections were photographed in the reflected-light brightfield observation mode of the Axio Imager.Z2m LSM 800 microscope (Carl Zeiss GmbH, Germany), running the software Zen Blue 2.5 (Carl Zeiss GmbH, Germany). The sample was firstly illuminated, by turning on the lighting unit HXP (120 V; consisting of a lamp module and an infrared filter), and within the Acquisition tab of the software, under the »widefield« screen (within the smart setup menu), the Reflected light (RL) Brightfield option was selected. The intensity of the lamp module was set to 12.8% and the shift value (under exposure time) was set to 100%, however the exposure times (t_{exp} in milliseconds) varied from sample to sample (see figure legends). Images were captured by the AxioCam 503 high performance microscopy camera in RGB colour mode, using the C Epiplan-Apochromat 10x/0.4

DIC M27 objective (Carl Zeiss GmbH, Germany) and a PI 10x/23 Eyepiece (Carl Zeiss GmbH, Germany) giving a total magnification of 100x (applied in all other microscopic techniques).

3.4.2. Widefield fluorescence observation

Prior to and after the hybridization, the sample cross sections were photographed in the widefield fluorescence observation mode, within the same Zeiss microscope system as is used in Section 3.1. The HXP unit (metal halide fluorescence light source) coupled with the cube filter set 10 (excitation: 450–490 nm, Beam-splitter: FT 510, emission: 515–565 nm; Carl Zeiss GmbH, Germany, 488010-9901-000) was turned on and within the Acquisition tab of the Zen Blue 2.5 software, under the »widefield« screen (within the smart setup menu), the FITC channel (519 nm) was selected. The intensity of the lamp module was set to 20.0% and the shift value (under exposure time) was set to 80%. Even though the exposure times varied from sample to sample, the same values (t_{exp} in ms) were used for photographs taken before and after the hybridization of a particular sample (see figure legends). Images were captured at a magnification of 100x using the AxioCam 503 camera in black and white mode and a green pseudo colour (false colour) was later added.

3.4.3. Laser scanning confocal fluorescence microscopy

After the hybridization, the sample cross sections were laser scanned by using the laser-scanning confocal fluorescent observation mode, within the same Zeiss microscope system as is used in Section 3.1. Firstly, the LSM 800 laser module LM URGB (contains fibre-coupled, pigtailed and collimated lasers) was turned on and the anti-vibration table Vision IsoStation (Newport, USA), on which the microscope system is positioned, was filled with 1 bar of pressure using compressed air. The manual tube slider (for switching between VIS/Camera) was placed into the camera position (100% camera) and within the Acquisition tab of the Zen Blue 2.5 software, under the »LSM« screen (within the smart setup menu), the FITC channel (519 nm) was selected. The intensity of the 488 nm argon diode laser (10 mW, class 3B), used for the excitation of FITC, was set to 2%. Emission detection was via the LSM 800 MAT Confocal MA-detection module (Carl Zeiss GmbH, Germany), which consists of a main beam splitter (MBS), a variable pinhole with automatic alignment, two variable secondary dichroics (VSD) placed at 10° angle to incident beam for most effective excitation light suppression; and an emission filter in front of each of the two multi-alkali (MA) PMT confocal channel detectors. The pinhole was set to 1 Airy unit (AU) with an opening diameter of 36 μ m. The digital gain of the PMT detectors was set to 0.9 (digital offset of 0), however the master gain settings (in V) varied from sample to sample (see figure legends). Finally, by defining the scanning borders (set first/last), a 3D model (at 100x magnification) was computer generated from a Z-stack of images, within an interval of 100 μ m (each image was 2.6 μ m apart).

3.4.4. Fluorescence intensities of sample layers

Fluorescence intensities were quantified from images obtained using widefield and confocal fluorescent microscopies. Firstly, the .tif format was opened, within the ImageJ distribution Fiji, and the entire surface of the embedded sample was measured, by marking the region of the entire sample, using the »Polygon selections tool« and by selecting the »Measure« function (preselect »Area« under the »Set measurements« options), within the »Analyse« menu.

Secondly, the fluorescence intensity (WFI for the widefield fluorescent mode and CFI for the confocal fluorescent mode) and the surface of a sample layer (defined by white triangles (see Figs. 1 to 8)) were quantified, by marking the region of this area using the »Polygon selections tool« and by selecting the »Measure« function

Fig. 1. Cross section images of the white coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment lead white, photographed prior to antibody hybridisation using the reflected-light brightfield observation (t_{exp} 1 ms; frame A) and the widefield fluorescence observation (t_{exp} 110 ms, frame B) modes. After antibody hybridisation, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (master gain 321 V, frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

(preselect »Area« and »Mean gray Value« under the »Set measurements« options), within the »Analyse« menu. The surface percentage of every sample layer (upper oil layer: S_0 ; oil paint layer: S_{O+P} ; or lower egg paint layer: S_{E+P}) was then calculated, by dividing its surface value with that of the entire sample.

Fluorescence intensity could only be compared between widefield fluorescence images made prior to and after the hybridization of a particular sample (exposure times were the same) or between layers within the same 3D model, generated using the confocal fluorescence microscopy. No comparisons could be made between different samples.

3.4.5. Surface topography scans and surface roughness parameters

After the hybridization, the topography of sample cross sections was laser scanned, by using the 405 nm laser scanning mode,

within the above mentioned Zeiss microscope system. Therefore, the same physical units and microscope system settings were employed as in Section 3.3. Within the applications tab of the Zen Blue 2.5 software, under the »topography«, the image acquisition option was selected. The intensity of the 405 nm violet diode laser (5 mW, class 3B), used for scanning, was set to 10%. The pinhole was set to 1 Airy unit (AU) with an opening diameter of 25 µm. Even though the master gain settings varied from sample to sample, its values were always close to around 250 ± 10 V. In order to engulf the entire surface topography of a cross section, the scanning borders (set first/last) were set to acquire a 700 µm long interval of Z-stack images (each image was 0.41 µm apart; 100x magnification) and these were saved as a CZI file format. This format was opened within the ImageJ distribution Fiji, and the images were reduced to 8-bits. Finally, by selecting the 3D Viewer

option, within the »Plugins« menu, a 3D surface topography model was generated. Moreover, from the CZI file format, surface roughness parameters were calculated in Fiji. These included the root mean square deviation (Rq; [μm]), the arithmetical mean deviation (Ra; [μm]), skewness of the assessed profile (Rsk), kurtosis of the assessed profile (Rku) and the total height of the profile (Rt). For their calculation, a height map was generated, by selecting the »Extended depth of field (EDF easy mode)« option within the »Plugins« menu. Based on the levelled surface of this map, the »SurfCharJ 1q« plugin calculated the above parameters.

3.5. Primary antibody validation

The new primary antibody batch was checked for its possible cross reactivity with other protein types, traditionally used as binders (gelatine and casein). Therefore the primary antibody for ovalbumin (C6534 Sigma Aldrich) was verified using the ELISA procedure (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay), according to the protocol published by Heginbotham et al. [20]. Firstly, 10 mg of standard protein (Gelatine from porcine skin G8150 Sigma Aldrich or Ovalbumin, from chicken egg white A5503 Sigma Aldrich or Casein from bovine milk C7078 Sigma Aldrich) was diluted in a 3.33 ml buffer (10 mM Tris–HCl, 1 mM EDTA, 6 M urea, 0.1% SDS), mixed well on a vortex and incubated at 37 °C for 5 h. Afterwards, 6.67 ml of sodium bicarbonate buffer (SBB: 100 mM of NaHCO₃, pH 9.6) was added, maintaining a ratio of 2:1. These solutions were then 100 fold diluted in SBB, to obtain a final protein concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, and were separately (80 μl of each into separate wells) applied onto Nunc-immunoTM microtiter plates (96 MicroWellTM Plates, MaxiSorpTM Sigma Aldrich; each sample and control (80 μl of MilliQ water) were applied in triplicates), and incubated overnight (2–8 °C). Afterwards, 300 μl of 5% calf serum albumin (CSA N4637, Sigma-Aldrich) blocking solution was added, to prevent unspecific binding of antibodies in the further steps of the procedure. For the indirect ELISA, our primary antibody in question (anti-ovalbumin C6534 Sigma Aldrich) was diluted in CSA, at a ratio of 1:500, and the alkaline phosphatase conjugated (AP) goat-anti-rabbit secondary antibody (A0418, Sigma Aldrich) was diluted in CSA, at a ratio of 1:600. For both primary and secondary antibodies, 100 μl were applied to each well. To obtain enzyme-substrate reaction, 100 μl of colourless p-NPP (P7998, Sigma Aldrich) was added to the wells and incubated for 30 min at the room temperature. The indicator was, in the case of a positive reaction, converted into a coloured product, by the reporting enzyme. Finally, the results were read using the Multiskan Sky (Thermo Scientific) spectrophotometer (optical density at 405 nm). Between each step, the wells were washed twice, using 300 μl of 0.02% Tween-20 in PBS, and twice with PBS only.

4. Results

4.1. Primary antibody validation

ELISA validation experiments showed no cross reactivity of primary anti-ovalbumin antibody (C6534, Sigma Aldrich) against other protein types traditionally used as binders (gelatine and casein). Specifically, for the standard targets of gelatine (G8150, Sigma Aldrich) and casein (C7078, Sigma Aldrich) the measured OD_{405nm} values were 0.014 ± 0.003 and 0.016 ± 0.002 , respectively. The signal from the negative control (MilliQ water) was also minimal at 0.016 ± 0.003 . The specificity for the standard target ovalbumin (A5503, Sigma Aldrich) however was strong reaching an OD_{405nm} value signal of 0.543 ± 0.013 . Therefore, this ordered batch of primary antibodies (C6534, Sigma Aldrich) was used for all further immunofluorescence microscopy experiments.

4.2. Immunofluorescence microscopy on dual layer micro samples

Firstly, micro samples which did not contain the additional third upper layer of pure linseed oil were examined.

In the reflected-light brightfield observation mode, prior to hybridisation, the surfaces of sample layers S_{O+P} (38.7% of total sample surface) and S_{E+P} (53.8% of total sample surface) of the white coloured micro sample, containing the pigment lead white, were not distinguishable from each other (Fig. 1A). They were slightly distinguishable in the widefield observation mode (Fig. 1B). After the antibody hybridisation process, the WFI_{E+P} increased from 27.7 to 41.6 (by 14.0), while the WFI_{O+P} increased from 21.1 to 31.0 (by 10.0). Therefore, the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure mainly enhanced the fluorescence of the egg paint layer (Fig. 1C). The difference between WFI_{E+P} and WFI_{O+P}, after the hybridisation, was 11.0 (prior to hybridisation this difference amounted to 6.7), while in the confocal observation mode this difference (CFI_{O+P} subtracted from CFI_{E+P}), after hybridisation, amounted to 15.6, achieving an even clearer localisation of the egg paint layer (Fig. 1D).

The topography of this cross section revealed (Fig. 1E) that the overall surface of this sample was smooth (rather low Rq (12.86 μm) and Ra values (10.23 μm)) (Table 2). Moreover, no 3D artefacts (holes, cracks) were found that would result in significant unspecific fluorescence.

In the reflected-light brightfield and widefield fluorescence modes, prior to antibody hybridisation, the surfaces of sample layers S_{O+P} (57.2% of total sample surface) and S_{E+P} (38.4% of total sample surface) of the blue coloured micro sample, containing the pigment prussian blue, were not distinguishable from each other (Fig. 2A and 2B). After the hybridisation process, the WFI_{E+P} increased from 4.4 to 17.4 (by 13.0), while the WFI_{O+P} only increased from 3.3 to 4.4 (by 1.1). Therefore, the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure exclusively enhanced the fluorescence of the egg paint layer (Fig. 2C). The difference between WFI_{E+P} and WFI_{O+P}, after the hybridisation, was 13.0 (prior to hybridisation this difference amounted to 1.1), while in the confocal observation mode this difference, after hybridisation, amounted to 25.0, achieving a flawless localisation of the egg paint layer (Fig. 2D). Moreover, in the confocal mode all of the unspecific fluorescence, originating from the resin's surface reflection was removed (present in the widefield fluorescence mode especially below the sample).

The topography of this cross section revealed (Fig. 2E) that the overall surface of this sample was very smooth (very low Ra value (4.88 μm) and a low Rq value (11.20 μm)) (Table 2). Moreover, no 3D artefacts (holes, cracks) were found that would result in significant unspecific fluorescence.

In the reflected-light brightfield and widefield fluorescence modes, prior to hybridisation, the surfaces of sample layers S_{O+P} (52.7% of total sample surface) and S_{E+P} (31.5% of total sample surface) of the bluish green coloured micro sample, containing the pigment verdigris, were not clearly distinguishable from each other (Fig. 3A and 3B). After the hybridisation process, the WFI_{E+P} strongly increased from 11.2 to 30.6 (by 19.4), while WFI_{O+P} slightly decreased from 14.2 to 12.3 (by 1.9). Therefore, the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure only enhanced the fluorescence of the egg paint layer (Fig. 3C). The difference between WFI_{E+P} and WFI_{O+P}, after the hybridisation, was 18.3 (prior to hybridisation this difference amounted to –3.0), while in the confocal observation mode this difference, after hybridisation, amounted to 12.9, which still resulted in a clear localisation of the egg paint layer (Fig. 3D). Moreover, all of the unspecific fluorescence, originating from resin's surface reflection was excluded in the confocal mode (Fig. 3D).

The topography of this cross section revealed (Fig. 3E) that the overall surface of this sample was rough (containing small inden-

Table 2

Surface roughness parameters, including the square deviation (Rq; [μm]), the arithmetical mean deviation (Ra; [μm]), skewness of the assessed profile (Rsk), kurtosis of the assessed profile (Rku) and the total height of the profile (Rt), calculated from 3D surface topography models of cross sections of micro (model) samples.

Surface of an embedded sample	Rq (μm)	Ra (μm)	Rsk	Rku	Rt
Dual layer micro samples					
Lead white	12.86	10.23	−0.94	6.44	190.87
Prussian blue	11.20	4.88	−8.21	90.51	184.48
Verdigris	14.58	6.52	1.05	47.07	313.75
Carmine lake	19.88	12.03	−3.12	20.15	317.60
Dragon's blood	75.94	51.60	2.11	5.65	597.08
Triple layer micro samples					
Vermilion	18.37	12.42	−1.38	18.07	318.93
Malachite	16.97	9.23	−3.59	52.03	354.29
Yellow ochre	22.56	9.73	−3.07	30.59	463.13
Madder lake	26.35	17.69	−1.45	22.81	466.14
Carbon black	17.68	9.35	−0.27	23.99	312.07

Fig. 2. Cross section images of the blue coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment prussian blue, photographed prior to antibody hybridisation using the reflected-light brightfield observation (t_{exp} 2.7 ms; frame A) and the widefield fluorescence observation (t_{exp} 1700 ms, frame B) modes. After antibody hybridisation, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (master gain 893 V, frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

Fig. 3. Cross section images of the bluish green coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment verdigris, photographed prior to antibody hybridisation using the reflected-light brightfield observation (t_{exp} 2 ms, frame A) and the widefield fluorescence observation (t_{exp} 600 ms, frame B) modes. After antibody hybridisation, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (master gain 593 V, frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

tations), but did not include any deep holes/cracks that would result in significant unspecific fluorescence (Rq value (14.58 µm)) (Table 2).

The immunofluorescence microscopy procedure did not succeed in solely marking the egg paint layer of the red coloured micro sample containing the pigment carmine lake. Instead, the entire sample's surface was illuminated equally by FITC conjugated secondary antibodies (WFI increase from ~1.7 to ~17.0 after the hybridisation) (Supplementary Figures 1B and 1C).

Supplementary Figure 1: Cross section images of the red coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment carmine lake, photographed prior to antibody hybridisation using the reflected-light brightfield observation (frame A) and the widefield

fluorescence observation (frame B) modes. After antibody hybridisation, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

Moreover, the oil paint layer (64.1% of total sample surface) of the dark red coloured micro sample, containing the pigment Dragon's blood, dissolved out of the resin during the resin polymerization step, which was performed in an oven at 50 °C. After its dissolution, only a deep hole (very high Rq (75.94 µm); Ra (51.60 µm) and Rt values (597.0)) with some fragments remained

in its place (Supplementary Figure 2E). Therefore, the success of the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure in marking only the egg paint layer could not be verified.

Supplementary Figure 2: Cross section images of the dark red coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment Dragon's blood, photographed prior to antibody hybridisation using the reflected-light brightfield observation (frame A) and the widefield fluorescence observation (frame B) modes. After antibody hybridisation, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

4.3. Immunofluorescence microscopy on triple layer micro samples

Secondly, micro samples, which contained the additionally added third upper layer of pure linseed oil, were examined.

In the widefield fluorescence mode, prior to antibody hybridisation, the surfaces of sample layers S_{O+P} (35.2% of total sample surface) and S_{E+P} (27.9% of total sample surface) of the yellowish red coloured micro sample, containing the pigment vermilion, were not distinguishable from each other (Fig. 4B). However, they were distinguishable in the reflected-light brightfield mode (Fig. 4A). After the hybridisation process, the WFI_{E+P} increased from 1.3 to 13.9 (by 12.6), while the WFI_{O+P} increased from 3.1 to 5.5 (by only 2.4). Therefore, the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure only enhanced the fluorescence of the egg paint layer (Fig. 4C). The difference between WFI_{E+P} and WFI_{O+P} , after the hybridisation, was 8.4 (prior to hybridisation this difference amounted to -1.8), while in the confocal observation mode this difference, after hybridisation, amounted to 22.7, achieving a flawless localisation of the egg paint layer (Fig. 4D). Moreover, the unspecific fluorescence resulting from the top S_O layer (36.4% of total sample surface) was almost completely reduced in the confocal mode (in the WF mode WFI_O was ~ 80).

The topography of this cross section revealed (Fig. 4E) that the overall surface of this sample was smooth, however there was a crack directly above the sample (Ra value of $12.42 \mu\text{m}$ and Rq value of $18.37 \mu\text{m}$) (Table 2). The narrow line of unspecific fluorescence resulting from this crack could be observed in the confocal mode.

In the reflected-light brightfield and widefield fluorescence modes, prior to hybridization, the surfaces of sample layers S_{O+P} (27.8% of total sample surface) and S_{E+P} (45.8% of total sample surface) of the bright green coloured micro sample, containing the pigment malachite, were not clearly distinguishable from each other (Figs. 5A and 5B). After the hybridisation process, the WFI_{E+P} increased from 14.7 to 20.5 (by 5.8), while the WFI_{O+P} increased from 13.5 to 14.7 (by 0.3). Therefore, the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure only enhanced the fluorescence of the egg paint layer although this enhancement was not very strong (Fig. 5C). The difference between WFI_{E+P} and WFI_{O+P} , after the hybridisation, was 6.7 (prior to hybridization this difference amounted to only 1.2), while in the confocal observation mode this difference, after hybridization, amounted to 11.3, achieving a much clearer localisation of the egg paint layer (Fig. 5D). Moreover, the unspecific fluorescence resulting from the top S_O layer (22.6% of total sample surface) was almost completely reduced in the confocal mode (in the widefield fluorescence mode WFI_O was ~ 70) and no unspecific fluorescence, originating from resin's surface reflection, was observed (present in the widefield mode especially above the sample).

The topography of this cross section revealed (Fig. 5E) that the oil paint layer contained small indentations and that there was a shallow gutter directly above the sample (Ra value of $9.23 \mu\text{m}$ and

Rq value of $16.97 \mu\text{m}$) (Table 2). The narrow bright line of unspecific fluorescence resulting from this gutter could clearly be observed in the confocal mode.

In the reflected-light brightfield mode, prior to hybridization, the surfaces of sample layers S_{O+P} (14.1% of total sample surface) and S_{E+P} (39.5% of total sample surface) of the yellowish brown coloured micro sample, containing the pigment yellow ochre, were not clearly distinguishable from each other (Fig. 6A). However, they were slightly distinguishable in the widefield fluorescence mode (Fig. 6B). After the hybridization process, the WFI_{E+P} increased from 8.8 to 15.7 (by 7.0), while the WFI_{O+P} decreased from 11.4 to 10.9 (by 0.5). Therefore, the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure only enhanced the fluorescence of the egg paint layer although this enchantment was mainly concentrated on small local cracks in the S_{E+P} (Fig. 6C). The difference between WFI_{E+P} and WFI_{O+P} , after the hybridization, was 4.8 (prior to hybridization this difference amounted to -2.6), while in the confocal observation mode this difference, after hybridization, amounted to 15.4, achieving a much clearer localization of the egg paint layer (Fig. 6D). Moreover, the unspecific fluorescence resulting from the top S_O layer (37.3% of total sample surface) was substantially reduced in the confocal mode (in the widefield mode WFI_O was ~ 38).

The topography of this cross section revealed (Fig. 6E) that the oil paint layer contained small but numerous indentations and that there was a deep crack directly above the sample (Ra value of $9.73 \mu\text{m}$ and Rq value of $22.56 \mu\text{m}$) (Table 2). The unspecific fluorescence resulting from this crack could clearly be observed in the confocal mode. Additionally there was a gutter directly below the sample and its unspecific fluorescence was visible only in the widefield fluorescence mode.

In the widefield fluorescence and reflected-light brightfield modes, prior to hybridization, the surfaces of sample layers S_{O+P} (32.1% of total sample surface) and S_{E+P} (35.16% of total sample surface) of the red coloured micro sample, containing the pigment madder lake, were slightly distinguishable from each other (Figs. 7A and 7B). After the hybridization process, the WFI_{E+P} increased from 18.4 to 24.8 (by 6.4), while the WFI_{O+P} increased from 16.1 to 18.7 (by only 2.6). Therefore, the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure significantly enhanced only the fluorescence of the egg paint layer although this enchantment was mainly concentrated on small local cracks in the S_{E+P} (Fig. 7C). The difference between WFI_{E+P} and WFI_{O+P} , after the hybridization, was 6.1 (prior to hybridization this difference amounted to 2.3), while in the confocal observation mode this difference, after hybridization, amounted to 12.3, achieving a clearer localization of the egg paint layer (Fig. 7D). Moreover, the unspecific fluorescence resulting from the top S_O layer (28.3% of total sample surface) was substantially reduced in the confocal mode (in the widefield mode WFI_O was ~ 66).

The topography of this cross section revealed (Fig. 7E) a relatively smooth surface with a deep crack directly above the sample (Ra value of $17.69 \mu\text{m}$ and Rq value of $26.35 \mu\text{m}$) (Table 2).

In the reflected-light brightfield and widefield fluorescence modes, prior to hybridization, the surfaces of sample layers S_{O+P} (35.2% of total sample surface) and S_{E+P} (19.24% of total sample surface) of the brownish-black coloured micro sample, containing the pigment carbon black, were not clearly distinguishable from each other (Figs. 8A and 8B). After the hybridization process, the WFI_{E+P} increased from 5.2 to 12.2 (by 7.0), while the WFI_{O+P} decreased from 9.0 to 8.3 (by 0.7). Therefore, the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure significantly enhanced only the fluorescence of the egg paint layer although this enchantment was very weak and was concentrated around larger pigment particles (Fig. 8C).

The difference between WFI_{E+P} and WFI_{O+P} , after the hybridization, was 4.0 (prior to hybridization this difference

Fig. 4. Cross section images of the yellowish red coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment vermilion, photographed prior to antibody hybridisation using the reflected-light brightfield observation (t_{exp} 2.3 ms, frame A) and the widefield fluorescence observation (t_{exp} 400 ms, frame B) modes. After antibody hybridisation, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (master gain 453 V, frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

amounted to 3.8), while in the confocal observation mode this difference, after hybridization, amounted to 31.1, achieving a flawless localization of the egg paint layer (Fig. 8D). Moreover, the unspecific fluorescence resulting from the top S_0 layer (32.3% of total sample surface) was reduced in the confocal mode (in the widefield mode WFI_0 was ~ 27).

The topography of this cross section revealed (Fig. 8E) that especially the egg paint layer contained small but numerous indentations and that there was a shallow crack directly above the sample (Ra value of 9.35 μm and Rq value of 17.68 μm) (Table 2).

5. Discussion

For 6 (lead white, Prussian blue, verdigris, Malachite, yellow ochre and carbon black) out of 10 micro samples, observed us-

ing the reflected-light brightfield mode, the sample layers S_{0+P} and S_{E+P} were not visually distinct enough to clearly identify one from the other. Moreover, for pigments prussian blue, verdigris, Vermilion, Malachite and carbon black, this distinction was also not possible in the widefield fluorescence observation mode. This therefore highlights the importance of the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure, to clearly identify only the epitope containing target layer. Moreover, the immunofluorescence microscopy procedure does not only highlight the target layer (egg paint layer), but because of its immunological principle, proves on the layer's binder substance (protein type and its biological source).

The immunofluorescence microscopy procedure in widefield observation mode was successful in its specificity and clarity in the presence of 8 out of 10 pigments. However, when the binder was combined with carmine lake and Dragon's blood, the immunoflu-

Fig. 5. Cross section images of the bright green coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment malachite, photographed prior to antibody hybridization using the reflected-light brightfield observation (t_{exp} 2.7 ms, frame A) and the widefield fluorescence observation (t_{exp} 500 ms, frame B) modes. After antibody hybridization, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (master gain 511 V, frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

orescence microscopy procedure failed to succeed. In the case of carmine lake, the entire sample’s surface (oil paint and egg paint layers) was illuminated equally by FITC conjugated secondary antibodies.

It could be that carmine lake powder, which is organic in nature, unspecifically adsorbs proteinous antibodies. In the case of Dragon’s blood, the oil paint layer dissolved out of the resin during the heating step at 50 °C. Dragons blood being the deep red latex of the specie of tree *Croton lechleri* (Müll. Arg.), contains a high concentration of phenolic compounds, which are highly susceptible to degradation especially at high temperatures [21].

For 4 (lead white, prussian blue, verdigris and vermilion) pigments out of the successful 8, the hybridisation step increased the fluorescence intensity of S_{E+P} (in widefield mode) for more than

12.0 (for verdigris the intensity increased for 19.4), while the intensity of S_{O+P} remained low (only increased by ~2.0). The exception was the S_{O+P} layer of the pigment lead white of which fluorescence intensity increased by 10.0, mainly because of the fact that the strong glowing fluorescence of the egg paint layer also brightened the neighbouring parts of the adjacent oil paint layer. Moreover, in the presence of the other 4 remaining pigments (malachite, yellow ochre, madder lake and carbon black) the intensity increase of the S_{E+P} layer was not as strong (by ~7), however it still significantly exceeded that of the S_{O+P} layer (by ~0.5).

For paint layers containing lead white, verdigris and carmine lake there have been reports of them causing a significant decrease in the efficiency of ELISA [14–16,18,19]. Nonetheless, as stated above, our immunofluorescence microscopy procedure worked ex-

Fig. 6. Cross section images of the yellowish brown coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment yellow ochre, photographed prior to antibody hybridization using the reflected-light brightfield observation (t_{exp} 2.9 ms, frame A) and the widefield fluorescence observation (t_{exp} 1000 ms, frame B) modes. After antibody hybridization, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (master gain 801 V, frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

ceptionally well for the micro samples containing lead white, and verdigris.

Moreover, for 6 of the 10 tested pigments, which exhibit a bright coloration (lead white, carmine lake, Dragon’s blood, vermilion, malachite and madder lake), there have been reports of them possessing a strong natural autofluorescence [5,12,17]. For example, this strong autofluorescence, prevented proteinous binder characterization on sample cross sections of old paintings using immunofluorescence microscopy [5]. In our study autofluorescence for pigments lead white, malachite, yellow ochre, madder lake and carbon black was observed, however its intensity was not high enough to disrupt or to significantly interfere with the immunofluorescence microscopy result. Interestingly, our results show that even dark pigments, for which the immunofluo-

rescence microscopy procedure was recommended [5], can exhibit a small degree of autofluorescence. For example, even before the hybridization of antibodies larger particles of the pigment carbon black clearly showed autofluorescence in the widefield mode. On the other hand, our study observed that carmine lake, which according to the literature should have exhibited a strong autofluorescence [12,17], was, prior to hybridization, completely dark in the widefield mode (no autofluorescence) (Supplementary Figure 1B).

When the confocal observation mode was used, the differences between fluorescence intensities of egg paint and oil paint layers, after antibody hybridization, were much greater to those obtained in the widefield fluorescence mode, achieving a much more specific and clear immunofluorescence microscopy picture (especially true for pigments Prussian blue, vermilion and carbon black).

Fig. 7. Cross section images of the red coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment madder lake, photographed prior to antibody hybridization using the reflected-light brightfield observation (t_{exp} 2.9 ms, frame A) and the widefield fluorescence observation (t_{exp} 500 ms, frame B) modes. After antibody hybridization, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (master gain 492 V, frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

Weaker improvements over the widefield mode were only observed for pigments lead white, malachite and verdigris (for verdigris intensity differences in confocal mode were below those of the widefield mode) and even in the case of verdigris, the confocal fluorescent 3D model was still clearer to that of widefield mode. This was because in the confocal mode nearly all of the unspecific fluorescence originating from resin's surface reflection, from pure oil binder (third oil layer from the bottom up) and from small indentations, was successfully removed. Additionally, the specific fluorescence of the egg paint layer contained no illumination glare that would have otherwise spread across different layers in the widefield mode. Nevertheless, the unspecific fluorescence originating from deep cracks could not have been avoided. It is known that confocal fluorescence microscopy can achieve a satisfying reduction of

nonspecific background emission [22]. In laser-scanning confocal microscopy, a monochromatic laser source is used to scan across a defined sample area, while the use of a very small aperture (pin-hole) in the optical path allows to detect light emitted within the focal plane at different sample depths and, at the same time, to discard the out-of-focus light [13]. In this way it is possible to obtain optical sections of the sample and reconstruct its 3D structure from the detected light independent of the position of the scanning spot [11]. Moreover, our Zeiss Laser Scanning Module (LSM) system is equipped with a spectral detection system in which the light emitted from the sample is spectrally decomposed by a prism before reaching the detectors. Sliders in front of the photomultiplier tubes allow a very precise selection (1 nm steps) of the wavelength range to be detected. This detection system gives much more flex-

Fig. 8. Cross section images of the brownish-black coloured micro (model) sample, containing the pigment carbon black, photographed prior to antibody hybridization using the reflected-light brightfield observation (t_{exp} 3.1 ms, frame A) and the widefield fluorescence observation (t_{exp} 1000 ms, frame B) modes. After antibody hybridization, the sample was again captured in the widefield fluorescence observation mode under the same illumination conditions (frame C) and was laser scanned using confocal fluorescence microscopy (master gain 721 V, frame D) and surface topography scans (frame E). Fluorescence intensities of sample layers in frames B, C and D are marked with white, horizontally directed triangles.

ibility compared to the standard filter-based fluorescence microscopes and allows for spectral scans within the focus plane. Nevertheless, because of its high costs, the confocal system is very rarely employed in the conservation sciences [11] and mostly widefield fluorescence systems are used [1,3,23,24].

Our study showed that in general, samples with smooth surfaces (containing lead white, Prussian blue and Vermilion) gave better results when assessed by immunofluorescence microscopy. Layers containing many indentations showed weaker fluorescence intensities especially in the widefield fluorescence mode (as seen for malachite, yellow ochre, madder lake and carbon black paint layers). The exception were paint layers containing verdigris, which despite of its overall rough surface, still exhibited strong specific fluorescence intensity. Kockaert et al. [5] similarly, stated

that pores, cracks or uneven surfaces have a detrimental effect on immunofluorescence microscopy and proposed precise successive polishing to eliminate such cavities. Nonetheless, the smoothness level of all of our samples was high enough to enable for a clear immunofluorescence microscopy picture. Lastly, our topography scans showed that most of the deep cracks appeared between the pure oil layer and the resin. It is well known that turpentine, which consists of resins dissolved in a volatile oil, can itself dissolve dried linseed oil [25,26]. Liquid polyester acrylic resin which during its curing uses the volatile methyl ethyl peroxide (MEK), as a catalyst, presents a similar chemical structure to the turpentine [27]. Therefore, during the curing process the polyester resin could dissolve some of the pure linseed oil, producing a crack between them.

6. Conclusions

Our study addressed the problematics of proteinous binder characterization, within a cross section of painted model samples, using immunofluorescence microscopy. Dual and triple layered model samples containing egg paint, oil paint and pure dried oil films were prepared. After antibody hybridization and employing immunofluorescence microscopy (in widefield and confocal observation modes) and surface topography scans, the following conclusions were drawn.

Immunofluorescence microscopy in the widefield observation mode selectively highlighted the egg paint layer when combined with 8 out of 10 tested pigments. The immunofluorescence microscopy result was especially clear and precise in the presence of pigments lead white, prussian blue, verdigris and vermilion. Even though, pigments lead white, malachite, yellow ochre, madder lake and carbon black exhibited a weak autofluorescence, it did not cause any interference. As was expected, the confocal observation mode surpassed that of the widefield mode, by which the unspecific fluorescence originating from resin's surface reflection, from pure oil binder and from small indentations was highly reduced. Lastly, 3D topography scans revealed that cross sections with smooth surfaces gave a much clearer immunofluorescence microscopy picture.

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Supplementary materials

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References

- [1] A. Heginbotham, V. Millay, M. Quick, The use of immunofluorescence microscopy and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay as complementary techniques for protein identification in artists' materials, *J. Am. Inst. Conserv.* 45 (2006) 89–105, doi:[10.1179/019713606806112522](https://doi.org/10.1179/019713606806112522).
- [2] L. Wang, J. Zhang, C. Li, H. Zhu, W. Wang, T. Wang, Synthesis, characterization and photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ film/Bi₂O₃ microgrid heterojunction, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 27 (2011) 59–63, doi:[10.1016/S1005-0302\(11\)60026-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1005-0302(11)60026-1).
- [3] J. Li, B. Zhang, Study of identification results of proteinous binding agents in Chinese painted cultural relics, *J. Cult. Herit.* 43 (2020) 73–79, doi:[10.1016/j.culher.2019.12.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2019.12.015).
- [4] M. Vagnini, L. Pitzurra, L. Cartechini, C. Miliani, B.G. Brunetti, A. Sgamellotti, Identification of proteins in painting cross-sections by immunofluorescence microscopy, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 392 (2008) 57–64, doi:[10.1007/s00216-008-2041-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-008-2041-9).
- [5] L. Kockaert, P. Gausset, M. Dubi-Rucquoy, Detection of ovalbumin in paint media by immunofluorescence, *Stud. Conserv.* 34 (1989) 183–188, doi:[10.1179/sic.1989.34.4.183](https://doi.org/10.1179/sic.1989.34.4.183).
- [6] P. Coremans, L'Agneau Mystique au laboratoire, in: D. Sikkel (Ed.), *Les Primitifs Flamands II*, Antwerp, 1953.
- [7] W. Hu, K. Zhang, H. Zhang, B. Zhang, B. Rong, Analysis of polychromy binder on Qin Shihuang's Terracotta Warriors by immunofluorescence microscopy, *J. Cult. Herit.* 16 (2015) 244–248, doi:[10.1016/j.culher.2014.05.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2014.05.003).
- [8] M. Palmieri, M. Vagnini, L. Pitzurra, B.G. Brunetti, L. Cartechini, Identification of animal glue and hen-egg yolk in paintings by use of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 405 (2013) 6365–6371, doi:[10.1007/s00216-013-7045-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-013-7045-4).
- [9] E. Albertini, L. Raggi, M. Vagnini, A. Sassolini, A. Achilli, G. Marconi, L. Cartechini, F. Veronesi, M. Falcinelli, B.G. Brunetti, C. Miliani, Tracing the biological origin of animal glues used in paintings through mitochondrial DNA analysis, in: *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, Springer, 2011, pp. 2987–2995, doi:[10.1007/s00216-010-4287-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-010-4287-2).
- [10] H.R. Petty, Fluorescence microscopy: established and emerging methods, experimental strategies, and applications in immunology, *Microsc. Res. Tech.* 70 (2007) 687–709, doi:[10.1002/jemt.20455](https://doi.org/10.1002/jemt.20455).
- [11] L. Cartechini, M. Palmieri, M. Vagnini, L. Pitzurra, Immunochemical methods applied to art-historical materials: identification and localization of proteins by ELISA and IFM, *Top. Curr. Chem.* 374 (2016) 1–21, doi:[10.1007/s41061-015-0006-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s41061-015-0006-y).
- [12] B. Ramírez-Barat, S. De La Viña, Characterization of proteins in paint media by immunofluorescence. A note on methodological aspects, *Stud. Conserv.* 46 (2001) 282–288, doi:[10.1179/sic.2001.46.4.282](https://doi.org/10.1179/sic.2001.46.4.282).
- [13] L. Cartechini, M. Vagnini, M. Palmieri, L. Pitzurra, T. Mello, J. Mazurek, G. Chiari, Immunodetection of proteins in ancient paint media, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 43 (2010) 867–876, doi:[10.1021/ar900279d](https://doi.org/10.1021/ar900279d).
- [14] F. Ren, N. Atlasevich, B. Baade, J. Loike, J. Arslanoglu, Influence of pigments and protein aging on protein identification in historically representative casein-based paints using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 408 (2016) 203–215, doi:[10.1007/s00216-015-9089-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-015-9089-0).
- [15] T. Špec, S. Peljhan, J. Vidič, N.L. Krajnc, M. Fonović, Č. Tavzes, P. Poret, CIM® monolith chromatography-enhanced ELISA detection of proteins in artists' paints: ovalbumin as a case study, *Microchem. J.* 127 (2016) 102–112, doi:[10.1016/j.microc.2016.02.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2016.02.004).
- [16] R. Rej, J.P. Breaudiere, Effects of metal ions on the measurement of alkaline phosphatase activity, *Clin. Chem.* 26 (1980) 423–428, doi:[10.1093/clinchem/26.3.0423](https://doi.org/10.1093/clinchem/26.3.0423).
- [17] C. Clementi, B. Doherty, P.L. Gentili, C. Miliani, A. Romani, B.G. Brunetti, A. Sgamellotti, Vibrational and electronic properties of painting lakes, *Appl. Phys. A Mater. Sci. Process.* 92 (2008) 25–33, doi:[10.1007/s00339-008-4474-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-008-4474-6).
- [18] M. Palmieri, M. Vagnini, L. Pitzurra, P. Rocchi, B.G. Brunetti, A. Sgamellotti, L. Cartechini, Development of an analytical protocol for a fast, sensitive and specific protein recognition in paintings by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 399 (2011) 3011–3023, doi:[10.1007/s00216-010-4308-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-010-4308-1).
- [19] H.Y. Lee, N. Atlasevich, C. Granzotto, J. Schultz, J. Loike, J. Arslanoglu, Development and application of an ELISA method for the analysis of protein-based binding media of artworks, *Anal. Methods* 7 (2015) 187–196, doi:[10.1039/c4ay01919a](https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ay01919a).
- [20] A. Heginbotham, V. Millay, M. Quick, The use of immunofluorescence microscopy and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays complementary techniques for protein identification in artists' materials, *J. Am. Inst. Conserv.* 45 (2006) 89–105, doi:[10.1179/019713606806112522](https://doi.org/10.1179/019713606806112522).
- [21] J.D. Escobar, C. Prieto, M. Pardo-Figueroa, J.M. Lagaron, Dragon's blood sap: storage stability and antioxidant activity, *Mol. A J. Synth. Chem. Nat. Prod. Chem.* 23 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.3390/MOLECULES23102641>.
- [22] J.B. Pawley, Fundamental limits in confocal microscopy, in: *Handb. Biol. Confocal Microsc.*, third ed., 2006, pp. 20–42, doi:[10.1007/978-0-387-45524-2_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-45524-2_2).
- [23] W. Hu, H. Zhang, B. Zhang, Identification of organic binders in ancient Chinese paintings by immunological techniques, *Microsc. Microanal.* 21 (2015) 1278–1287, doi:[10.1017/S1431927615015147](https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927615015147).
- [24] D. Magrini, S. Bracci, I.C.A. Sandu, Fluorescence of organic binders in painting cross-sections, *Procedia Chem.* 8 (2013) 194–201, doi:[10.1016/j.proche.2013.03.025](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proche.2013.03.025).
- [25] C. Qiu, J. Smuts, K.A. Schug, Analysis of terpenes and turpentine using gas chromatography with vacuum ultraviolet detection, *J. Sep. Sci.* 40 (2017) 869–877, doi:[10.1002/jssc.201601019](https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.201601019).
- [26] M. Frances, Y. Gardere, E. Duret, L. Leroyer, T. Cabaret, M. Rubini, A.B. Bi Athomo, B. Charrier, Effect of heat treatment on Pinus pinaster rosin: a study of physico chemical changes and influence on the quality of rosin linseed oil varnish, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 155 (2020) 112789, doi:[10.1016/j.indcrop.2020.112789](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2020.112789).
- [27] S.M. Kidwell, J.A. Moore, J.R. Moore, Inexpensive field technique for polyester resin peels of structures in unconsolidated sediments, *Mar. Geol.* 64 (1985) 351–359, doi:[10.1016/0025-3227\(85\)90113-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(85)90113-6).